

Spectroscopic and X-ray crystal structure studies of 2-aminothiazole-3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid derivatives

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Interaction of 2-aminothiazole (AT) base with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid (DNB) and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) gave 1 : 1 molecular species. The salts were investigated using IR, NMR and UV-Vis spectroscopic techniques. Proton transfer occurred from the acid to the hetero nitrogen atom of the aminothiazole to form a Lewis salt. The crystal structure of AT-DNB (1) and AT-DNS (2) were determined by single crystal X-ray diffraction. Both two compounds crystallize in a monoclinic cell, (space group $P2_1/c$). The structures were determined by direct methods and refined to $R = 0.055$ for 1 and $R = 0.074$ for 2.

Solid charge transfer complexes especially those of organic donors and acceptors are commonly studied by different spectroscopic tools^{1,2}. Many of these complexes were also investigated by X-ray crystal analysis²⁻⁷. Importance of these charge transfer complexes is retained to their special type of interaction, which is accompanied by transfer of an electron from the donor to the acceptor and/or proton transfer.

Interaction of 2-aminobenzothiazole with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid was found to give a 1 : 1 adduct^{2,5}. X-Ray analysis of the complex showed that the acid protonated the hetero nitrogen atom of the benzothiazole ring to give a non-centrosymmetric proton-transfer species⁵. Spectroscopic and X-ray analysis of the molecular species formed from 2-aminobenzimidazole and trinitrobenzene showed the formation of a CT complex with $\pi-\pi^*$ type of interaction. On the other hand, picric acid protonated the hetero N atom of the benzimidazole ring to give an ion pair³. In this paper, we report the synthesis, spectroscopic and crystal structure determination of the 1 : 1 molecular salts of 2-aminothiazole with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acids (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

IR and NMR spectra :

1 : 1 Molecular salts were prepared by refluxing equimolar solutions of 2-aminothiazole (AT) and 3,5-

Scheme 1

dinitrobenzoic acid (DNB) and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS). The IR spectra of the compounds showed characteristic bands due to the C=N group, symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequencies of NH, NO and CO functional groups of the AT part, and the acids moieties (Table 1). It is interesting to note that the higher energy C=N band of the base moiety disappeared, while the lower frequency band was shifted to higher frequency indicating an increase in the bond order. On the other hand, the ν_{asym} (NO) bands of the nitrobenzenes were shifted to lower frequency values presumably due to the increased polarization of the NO₂ group. In addition, the IR spectra of AT-DNB (1) and AT-DNS (2) salts showed that the bands due to the CO groups were shifted to lower frequency. The ¹H NMR spectra of the reported salts

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Table 1. Important IR and NMR data for AT, acids and their molecular salts

Compd.	IR data (cm ⁻¹)					NMR data (ppm) ^b	
	v(NH)	v(C=O)	v(C=N)	v(OH)	v(NO)	Base	Acid
AT	3410(s)	-	1628(s)	-	-	7.39 (2H, bs)	-
	3290(s)		1520(s)			6.90 (1H, d)	
						6.45 (1H, d)	
DNB	-	1705	-	3094(m)	1628(m)	-	11.30 (1H, bs)
					1543(s)		8.97 (1H, t)
					1412(m)		8.89 (1H, t)
					1350 (s)		8.87 (1H, t)
DNS	-	1682	-	3572(m)	1605(s)	-	11.21 (1H, bs)
				3449(m)	1535(s)		8.70 (1H, d)
				3101(m)	1351(sh)		8.66 (1H, d)
					1342(s)		5.96 (1H, bs)
AT-DNB	3334(m)	1539(s)	1570(m)	-	1634(sh)	7.42 (2H, bs)	8.97 (1H, t)
	3310(m)				1620(s)	7.00 (1H, d)	8.96 (1H, t)
	3125(m)				1376(sh)	6.59 (1H, d)	8.88 (1H, t)
					1346(s)		
AT-DNS	3323(m)	1520(s)	1572(sh)	3364(s)	1645(sh)	7.09 (1H, d)	8.67 (1H, d)
	3154(m)				1620(s)	6.72 (1H, d)	8.64 (1H, d)
	3125(m)				1500(sh)	3.94 (2H, bs)	8.04 (1H, bs)
					1342(s)		

^as, strong; m, medium; sh, shoulder.

^bs, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; m, multiplet; b, broad.

(Table 1) displayed signals due to both the base and acid moieties with the appropriate shifts. The ¹H NMR spectrum of AT-DNS showed that the transfer of the carboxylic proton to the hetero N of the AT and not the proton of the hydroxyl group. This proton transfer was confirmed by the X-ray crystal structure (*vide infra*). The hydroxyl group exerted a shift of 2.08 ppm to lower field. This shift could be due to hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl proton and oxygen of the carboxylate group.

Description of the structures of AT-DNB and AT-DNS salts :

The crystal structure of AT-DNB and AT-DNS salts were determined by X-ray analysis. The crystallographic data for the X-ray crystal structure of AT-DNB and AT-DNS derivatives are presented in Table 2. The ORTEP representations of the two compounds are illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The fractional atomic coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters for AT-DNB and AT-DNS are given in Tables 3 and 4. Anisotropic thermal parameters for AT-DNB and AT-DNS are given in Tables 5 and 6. Selected bond lengths and angles for the two compounds are given in Tables 7 and 8. The interesting features in the structure of AT-DNB salt are :

Table 2. Crystal parameters and X-ray diffraction data for AT-DNB and AT-DNS salts

Crystal parameters	AT-DNB	AT-DNS
Empirical formula	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ O ₆ S	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ O ₇ S
Fw	312.20	328.20
Space group	P2 ₁ /c	P2 ₁ /c
A/Å	6.6466(4)	8.5078(4)
B/Å	8.9431(4)	22.0137(13)
C/Å	21.6015(13)	12.4309(5)
α/deg	90.00	90.00
β/deg	95.140(2)	145.148(2)
γ/deg	90.00	90.00
V/Å ³	1278.86(12)	1298.33(11)
Z	4	4
T/K	298	298
ρ _{calc} /g cm ⁻³	1.601	1.679
μ/cm ⁻¹	0.28	0.29
R ^a	0.055	0.074
R _w ^b	0.058	0.043
(MoKα)/Å	0.71073	0.71073

$$^a R = \frac{\sum [|F_o| - |F_c|]}{\sum |F_o|}$$

$$^b R_w = \left[\frac{\sum w(|F_o| - |F_c|)^2}{\sum w|F_o|^2} \right]^{1/2}; w = 1/\delta^2(F_o)^2 + 0.0300 * (F_o)^2.$$

Fig. 1. ORTEP drawing of the AT-DNB salt with the atom numbering scheme.

Fig. 2. ORTEP drawing of the AT-DNS salt with the atom numbering scheme.

Table 3. Fractional atomic coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) with e.s.d's in parentheses for AT-DNB salt

	X	Y	Z	U_{eq}
S(1)	0.46961(2)	0.770485(18)	1.028120(6)	0.06422(8)
N(2)	0.52146(6)	0.67107(4)	0.921292(16)	0.0448(2)
O(3)	0.14555(6)	0.50696(5)	0.580803(15)	0.0732(2)
O(4)	-0.27465(5)	0.56828(4)	0.828186(13)	0.05099(18)
N(5)	0.51737(6)	0.28891(4)	0.770457(18)	0.0468(2)
O(6)	-0.04131(5)	0.47010(4)	0.897188(14)	0.0634(2)
C(7)	0.20909(6)	0.40192(5)	0.804565(19)	0.0397(2)
O(8)	0.54717(6)	0.23165(4)	0.821686(18)	0.0738(2)
O(9)	0.63354(5)	0.27843(4)	0.729877(15)	0.05801(19)
C(10)	0.09656(7)	0.49245(5)	0.685376(19)	0.0393(2)
O(11)	-0.11343(7)	0.61802(4)	0.612021(16)	0.0752(3)
C(12)	0.32955(6)	0.37406(5)	0.756788(19)	0.0377(2)
C(13)	-0.10793(7)	0.50695(5)	0.84362(2)	0.0436(2)
N(14)	0.79530(7)	0.62422(6)	0.99320(2)	0.0733(3)
C(15)	-0.03097(6)	0.52113(5)	0.73117(19)	0.0392(2)
N(16)	0.03886(7)	0.54373(5)	0.621577(17)	0.0505(2)
C(17)	0.27832(7)	0.41911(5)	0.696764(19)	0.0404(2)
C(18)	0.61455(7)	0.67921(6)	0.97813(2)	0.0476(3)
C(19)	0.02647(6)	0.47584(5)	0.791584(18)	0.0374(2)
C(20)	0.28069(7)	0.79420(6)	0.96881(2)	0.0616(3)
C(21)	0.33263(7)	0.73589(6)	0.91622(2)	0.0540(3)
H(14A)	0.8503(7)	0.5741(5)	0.9639(2)	0.050(2)
H(14B)	0.8513(9)	0.6285(7)	1.0320(3)	0.094(2)
H(7)	0.2503(10)	0.3706(7)	0.8463(3)	0.050(2)
H(15)	-0.1579(10)	0.5711(7)	0.7218(3)	0.050(2)
H(17)	0.3674(10)	0.3991(7)	0.6651(3)	0.050(2)
H(21)	0.2413(10)	0.7413(7)	0.8792(3)	0.050(2)
H(20)	0.1517(10)	0.8419(7)	0.9700(3)	0.050(2)
H(2)	0.5717(8)	0.6261(7)	0.8853	0.050(2)

Table 4. Fractional atomic coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) with e.s.d's in parentheses for AT-DNS salt

	X	Y	Z	U_{eq}
S(1)	0.44245(4)	0.223188(8)	0.43894(2)	0.11325(12)
O(2)	0.82669(8)	-0.013189(18)	0.69096(6)	0.0884(3)
O(3)	1.04761(9)	0.07137(2)	0.90937(6)	0.0895(3)
O(4)	0.68692(10)	0.09532(2)	0.13930(6)	0.1360(3)
O(5)	1.10374(9)	0.15959(2)	0.85654(6)	0.1096(3)
N(6)	0.28962(11)	0.21196(2)	0.15436(7)	0.0830(3)
N(7)	0.57027(10)	-0.06599(2)	0.34933(7)	0.0777(3)
N(8)	0.75815(11)	0.12213(3)	0.26474(7)	0.0854(3)
O(9)	0.81937(10)	0.17609(2)	0.30307(7)	0.1283(3)
C(10)	0.80539(11)	0.01827(3)	0.58755(8)	0.0575(3)
O(11)	0.61444(10)	-0.10179(2)	0.45014(6)	0.1164(3)
C(12)	0.28279(12)	0.18192(3)	0.24517(8)	0.1187(4)

Table-4 (contd.)

C(13)	0.66711(11)	0.02928(3)	0.31498(7)	0.0581(3)
N(14)	0.17237(13)	0.12819(3)	0.19420(8)	0.1013(4)
C(15)	0.41901(13)	0.26747(3)	0.23402(9)	0.1031(4)
O(16)	0.43310(10)	-0.08011(2)	0.19000(6)	0.1315(3)
C(17)	0.88706(11)	0.11296(2)	0.53474(8)	0.0654(3)
C(18)	0.90504(11)	0.07856(2)	0.64065(8)	0.1187(3)
C(19)	0.77032(11)	0.08704(3)	0.37432(8)	0.0651(3)
C(20)	0.51163(13)	0.28106(3)	0.38703(9)	0.1060(4)
C(21)	0.68341(11)	-0.00497(2)	0.41954(8)	0.0587(3)
C(22)	1.02890(12)	0.10658(3)	0.81319(8)	0.0727(4)
H(13)	0.58274(11)	0.01193(3)	0.20217(9)	0.050(3)
H(17)	0.95191(13)	0.15407(3)	0.56749(5)	0.050(3)
H(14A)	0.0994(12)	0.1105(3)	0.0937(8)	0.050(3)
H(14B)	0.1812(12)	0.1106(3)	0.2578(8)	0.050(3)
H(6)	0.2215(11)	0.1933(3)	0.0545(8)	0.050(3)
H(3)	0.9577(11)	0.0286(3)	0.8339(8)	0.050(3)
H(20)	0.6031(13)	0.3191(3)	0.4524(10)	0.050(3)
H(15)	0.4462(13)	0.2954(3)	0.1898(10)	0.050(3)

the ring of the thiazole moiety is tilted towards the benzene ring of DNB from the hetero nitrogen side. The bond displacement between the N(2)-O(4) and N(2)-C(13)

are 2.6861(5) and 3.4319(6), respectively, while distance between C(13)-C(18) is 3.8960(6).

The contents of one unit cell of AT-DNB salt are shown in Fig. 3. At the center of this view, it can be noticed that each two aminothiazole molecules and each two dinitrobenzoic species are located overlapped and parallel to each other. Therefore, from such arrangement we can conclude that the type of interaction between AT and DNB was due to proton transfer only to form ion pair. As shown in Fig. 3, the chains of molecules are linked by N-H...O or C-H...O hydrogen bonds.

The crystal structure of AT-DNS salt (Fig. 2) showed that both the aminothiazole and dinitrosalicylic moieties are located parallel to each other. The contents of one unit cell of AT-DNS salt are shown in Fig. 4. It showed that the chains of molecules are linked by N-H...O or C-H...O hydrogen bonds. At the center of this view, each AT moiety is placed parallel to a dinitrosalicylic part but it displaced in a position to form hydrogen bonding between the protonated hetero nitrogen of the aminothiazole ring (NH) with the carbonyl of the carboxylic group.

The intermolecular distance between O(5) and H(6) is 1.836(5). From torsion angles between the different molecules, the two AT and DNS moieties are planar and the

Table 5. Anisotropic thermal parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) with e.s.d's in parentheses for AT-DNB salt

	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{12}	U_{13}	U_{23}
S(1)	0.05834(8)	0.09712(12)	0.03714(7)	0.02077(8)	0.00793(5)	-0.01195(7)
N(2)	0.0468(2)	0.0567(2)	0.03111(18)	0.00949(19)	0.00785(16)	-0.00188(17)
O(3)	0.0755(3)	0.1064(3)	0.03839(19)	0.0009(2)	0.01864(18)	0.0056(2)
O(4)	0.04519(19)	0.0678(2)	0.04027(17)	0.02003(17)	0.01073(14)	0.00268(15)
N(5)	0.0432(2)	0.0481(2)	0.0496(2)	0.00532(18)	0.01221(18)	-0.00577(19)
O(6)	0.0541(2)	0.1016(3)	0.03463(17)	0.0296(2)	0.00975(15)	0.00496(18)
C(7)	0.0428(2)	0.0408(2)	0.0356(2)	0.0008(2)	0.00778(18)	0.00024(19)
O(8)	0.0781(3)	0.0873(3)	0.0567(2)	0.0423(2)	0.01970(19)	0.0209(2)
O(9)	0.04288(18)	0.0742(2)	0.0580(2)	0.00586(17)	0.02015(16)	-0.00873(17)
C(10)	0.0456(3)	0.0381(2)	0.0342(2)	-0.0061(2)	0.00652(18)	0.00016(19)
O(11)	0.0899(3)	0.0860(3)	0.0482(2)	0.0287(2)	-0.0027(2)	0.0086(2)
C(12)	0.0351(2)	0.0362(2)	0.0419(2)	0.00121(19)	0.00903(18)	-0.00140(19)
C(13)	0.0432(3)	0.0499(3)	0.0378(2)	0.0047(2)	0.0104(2)	-0.0021(2)
N(14)	0.0610(3)	0.1186(4)	0.0397(2)	0.0393(3)	0.0014(2)	-0.0066(3)
C(15)	0.0375(2)	0.0392(3)	0.0407(2)	-0.0003(2)	0.00666(18)	0.0000(2)
N(16)	0.0594(3)	0.0543(3)	0.0374(2)	-0.0064(2)	0.00521(19)	0.00231(19)
C(17)	0.0429(3)	0.0390(2)	0.0401(2)	-0.0058(2)	0.01515(19)	-0.00489(19)
C(18)	0.0470(3)	0.0615(3)	0.0343(2)	0.0106(2)	0.0084(2)	0.0020(2)
C(19)	0.0382(2)	0.0381(2)	0.0362(2)	0.00069(19)	0.00916(18)	-0.00153(19)
C(20)	0.0462(3)	0.0902(4)	0.0482(3)	0.0217(3)	0.0070(2)	-0.0048(3)
C(21)	0.0445(3)	0.0788(4)	0.0383(2)	0.0126(3)	0.0014(2)	0.0000(2)

Table 6. Anisotropic thermal parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) with e.s.d's in parentheses for AT-DNS salt

	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{12}	U_{13}	U_{23}
S(1)	0.09194(14)	0.04493(10)	0.06020(10)	-0.00647(10)	0.06808(11)	-0.00711(9)
O(2)	0.0645(3)	0.0432(3)	0.0472(3)	-0.0028(2)	0.0479(3)	0.0006(2)
O(3)	0.0674(3)	0.0491(3)	0.0426(2)	-0.0062(2)	0.0467(3)	-0.0044(2)
O(4)	0.1066(4)	0.0687(3)	0.0699(3)	0.0076(3)	0.0800(3)	0.0080(3)
O(5)	0.0855(4)	0.0468(3)	0.0568(3)	-0.0191(3)	0.0612(3)	-0.0167(2)
N(6)	0.0638(4)	0.0390(3)	0.0428(3)	-0.0033(3)	0.0463(3)	-0.0036(2)
N(7)	0.0492(3)	0.0450(3)	0.0441(3)	-0.0038(3)	0.0388(3)	-0.0057(3)
N(8)	0.0547(3)	0.0549(4)	0.0463(3)	0.0072(3)	0.0431(3)	0.0106(3)
O(9)	0.0963(4)	0.0509(3)	0.0724(3)	-0.0056(3)	0.0726(3)	0.0054(3)
C(10)	0.0338(3)	0.0397(3)	0.0316(3)	0.0064(3)	0.0270(3)	0.0056(3)
O(11)	0.0902(4)	0.0428(3)	0.0598(3)	-0.0109(3)	0.0608(3)	-0.0043(2)
C(12)	0.0500(4)	0.0500(3)	0.0500(3)	0.0000(3)	0.0000(3)	0.0000(3)
C(13)	0.0337(3)	0.0454(4)	0.0297(3)	0.0070(3)	0.0259(3)	0.0028(3)
N(14)	0.0769(4)	0.0483(4)	0.0522(4)	-0.0143(3)	0.0555(4)	-0.0081(3)
C(15)	0.0796(4)	0.0349(4)	0.0621(4)	-0.0060(4)	0.0634(4)	-0.0030(3)
O(16)	0.1019(4)	0.0647(3)	0.0622(3)	-0.0305(3)	0.0687(3)	-0.0278(3)
C(17)	0.0393(4)	0.0400(4)	0.0382(3)	0.0012(3)	0.0322(3)	0.0020(3)
C(18)	0.0500(3)	0.0500(3)	0.0500(3)	0.0000(3)	0.0000(3)	0.0000(3)
C(19)	0.0403(4)	0.0433(4)	0.0365(3)	0.0058(3)	0.0331(3)	0.0078(3)
C(20)	0.0815(4)	0.0359(4)	0.0627(4)	-0.0119(4)	0.0634(4)	-0.0112(3)
C(21)	0.0346(3)	0.0338(3)	0.0354(3)	0.0009(3)	0.0286(3)	-0.0015(3)
C(22)	0.0450(4)	0.0491(4)	0.0385(4)	0.0001(3)	0.0344(3)	-0.0014(3)

Table 7. Selected bond lengths ($\text{\AA}$) and angles ($^\circ$) for AT-DNB salt

S(1)-C(18)	1.7166(4)	O(11)-N(16)	1.2130(5)
S(1)-C(20)	1.7248(5)	C(12)-C(17)	1.3712(6)
N(2)-C(18)	1.3265(5)	C(13)-C(19)	1.5228(5)
N(2)-C(21)	1.3780(6)	N(14)-C(18)	1.3119(6)
O(3)-N(16)	1.2242(5)	C(15)-C(19)	1.3870(5)
O(4)-C(13)	1.2545(5)	C(20)-C(21)	1.3235(6)
N(5)-O(8)	1.2193(5)	N(2)-H(2)	0.9600(4)
N(5)-O(9)	1.2226(5)	N(5)-C(12)	1.4696(5)
O(6)-C(13)	1.2457(5)	N(14)-H(14A)	0.881(5)
C(7)-C(12)	1.3843(5)	N(14)-H(14B)	0.886(6)
C(7)-C(19)	1.3885(6)	C(10)-C(17)	1.3773(6)
C(10)-C(15)	1.3831(5)	O(9)-C(21)	3.2066(6)
S(1)-O(3)	3.2148(4)	O(11)-C(20)	3.5105(7)
S(1)-O(8)	3.2563(5)	C(13)-N(14)	3.5108(7)
N(2)-O(4)	2.6861(5)	C(13)-C(18)	3.8960(6)
N(2)-C(13)	3.4319(6)	N(16)-C(20)	3.5440(6)
O(6)-N(14)	2.7899(6)		
C(18)-S(1)-C(20)	90.20(2)	O(6)-C(13)-C(19)	117.01(4)
C(18)-N(2)-C(21)	113.36(4)	C(10)-C(15)-C(19)	118.95(4)
O(8)-N(5)-O(9)	123.84(4)	O(3)-N(16)-O(11)	123.58(4)
O(8)-N(5)-C(12)	117.77(4)	C(10)-C(17)-C(12)	116.64(4)

Table-7 (contd.)

O(9)-N(5)-C(12)	118.39(4)	S(1)-C(18)-N(2)	111.52(3)
C(12)-C(7)-C(19)	119.26(4)	S(1)-C(18)-N(14)	125.12(4)
C(15)-C(10)-C(17)	122.99(4)	N(2)-C(18)-N(14)	123.36(4)
N(5)-C(12)-C(7)	118.76(4)	C(7)-C(19)-C(13)	119.87(4)
N(5)-C(12)-C(17)	118.48(4)	C(7)-C(19)-C(15)	119.41(4)
C(7)-C(12)-C(17)	122.74(4)	C(13)-C(19)-C(15)	120.73(4)
O(4)-C(13)-O(6)	126.48(4)	S(1)-C(20)-C(21)	111.13(4)
O(4)-C(13)-C(19)	116.51(4)	N(2)-C(21)-C(20)	113.79(4)

Table 8. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for AT-DNS salt

S(1)-C(12)	1.7190(5)	N(14)-H(14A)	1.3079(7)
S(1)-C(20)	1.7246(6)	N(14)-H(14B)	1.3670(7)
O(2)-C(10)	1.3089(5)	C(10)-C(18)	1.3814(6)
O(3)-C(22)	1.2972(6)	O(2)-N(14)	1.3249(7)
O(4)-N(8)	1.2320(5)	O(4)-C(20)	1.3875(6)
O(5)-C(22)	1.2224(6)	O(5)-C(20)	1.3881(6)
N(6)-C(12)	1.3264(6)	O(16)-C(20)	1.5006(6)
N(6)-C(15)	1.3757(6)	O(11)-C(15)	0.906(5)
N(7)-O(11)	1.2262(5)	O(11)-C(12)	1.4217(6)
N(7)-O(16)	1.2216(5)	O(9)-C(15)	0.884(5)
N(7)-C(21)	1.4527(6)	C(12)-N(14)	0.809(5)
N(8)-O(9)	1.2251(5)	C(13)-C(19)	1.4138(7)
N(8)-C(19)	1.4658(6)	C(13)-C(21)	2.8865(6)
S(1)-O(11)	3.2025(4)	C(15)-C(20)	3.3918(6)
O(3)-N(14)	2.9345(6)	C(17)-C(18)	3.4321(6)
O(5)-N(6)	2.7397(5)	C(17)-C(19)	3.3399(7)
C(17)-C(20)	3.8303(7)	C(18)-C(22)	3.5088(6)
C(15)-C(17)	3.9113(7)	N(6)-H(6)	3.4977(6)
C(11)-N(14)	3.0657(6)	C(10)-C(21)	3.3358(7)
O(9)-C(20)	3.3955(6)		
C(12)-S(1)-C(20)	90.84(3)	N(6)-C(15)-C(20)	113.44(5)
C(12)-N(6)-C(15)	114.50(4)	C(18)-C(17)-C(19)	118.82(5)
O(11)-N(7)-O(16)	121.82(5)	C(10)-C(18)-C(17)	121.42(4)
O(11)-N(7)-C(21)	119.75(4)	C(10)-C(18)-C(22)	119.58(4)
O(16)-N(7)-C(21)	118.43(4)	C(17)-C(18)-C(22)	119.00(5)
O(4)-N(8)-O(9)	123.94(5)	N(8)-C(19)-C(13)	118.41(4)
O(4)-N(8)-C(19)	117.70(5)	N(8)-C(19)-C(17)	119.44(5)
O(9)-N(8)-C(19)	118.37(4)	C(13)-C(19)-C(17)	122.15(4)
O(2)-C(10)-C(18)	120.03(4)	S(1)-C(20)-C(15)	110.84(4)
O(2)-C(10)-C(21)	123.20(5)	N(7)-C(21)-C(10)	121.75(4)
C(18)-C(10)-C(21)	116.77(4)	N(7)-C(21)-C(13)	116.58(4)
S(1)-C(12)-N(6)	110.37(4)	C(10)-C(21)-C(13)	121.67(4)
S(1)-C(12)-N(14)	125.40(4)	O(3)-C(22)-C(5)	123.20(5)
N(6)-C(12)-N(14)	124.22(5)	O(3)-C(22)-C(18)	115.87(5)
C(19)-C(13)-C(21)	119.15(4)	O(5)-C(22)-C(18)	120.93(5)

Fig. 3. View of the packing arrangements of the AT-DNB molecules.

separations between the atoms of both species are almost the same. In the DNS part, the C–O bond length is in the order : C(22)–O(5) < C(22)–O(3) < C(10)–O(2), which is the order of decreasing of bond order. Thus, it can be concluded that protonation of the hetero nitrogen atom of aminothiazole occurred from the carboxylic proton. This is consistent with the ^1H NMR spectrum of the compound. Also, the increasing of the bond distance of C(22)–O(3) relative to C(22)–O(5) of the same carboxylic group indicated the presence of hydrogen bonding with the hydroxyl group, Fig. 2.

Electronic absorption studies :

The UV and visible absorption spectra of 1 and 2 exhibited changes in shape, intensity and position of bands in comparison with the spectra of the free base and acids. The spectra showed that the band due to benzene moiety of the acceptor part was red shifted, whereas the second band due to the intramolecular charge transfer within the nitrobenzene derivative was blue shifted (Table 9). On the other hand, the π - π^* of the aminothiazole was red shifted in the spectra of the salts. In case of AT-DNS salt, this band was obscured underneath of the visible band. The visible band of the salt derived from the dinitrosalicylic acid appeared at 327 nm was due to dinitrosalicylate anion part of the molecule (sodium dinitrosalicylate itself showed a broad band at 340 nm).

Fig. 4. View of the packing arrangements of the AT-DNS molecules.

Table 9. UV-Vis data for AT, acids and their salts

Compd.	UV-Vis data, $\lambda(\text{nm})$
AT	255
DNB	243, 283
DNS	225, 337
AT-DNB	231, 250
AT-DNS	248, 327

This can, thus, be explained by a proton transfer from the carboxylic group of DNS to the nitrogen of the AT ring as shown from the X-ray analysis^{2,3}.

Experimental

Reagents : The 2-aminothiazole (AT), 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid (DNB) and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) were purchased from Aldrich. All the solvents were of analytical reagent grade and were purified by

standard methods.

Instruments : IR measurements (KBr discs) were carried out on a Unicam-Mattson 1000 FT-IR spectrometer. Electronic absorption spectra were measured on a Unicam UV2-300 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Samples of concentration $ca. 5 \times 10^{-4} M$ in DMSO were used for measurements. NMR measurements were performed on a Varian 300 MHz spectrophotometer.

Samples were dissolved in $(CD_3)_2SO$ with TMS as internal reference. Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer.

Synthesis of compounds : The reported compounds were prepared by mixing a hot saturated solution of 2-aminothiazole (0.01 mol dissolved in a minimum amount of hot absolute ethanol) with an equimolar amount of the acid also dissolved in a minimum amount of ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for $ca. 30$ min. Solid salts were precipitated from the reaction mixture on cooling. The compounds were recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. Colour and m.p. : AT-DNB; orange-yellow, 209–210°C and AT-DNS; yellow, 164–165°C. Elemental analysis of the isolated salts revealed the formation of 1 : 1 salts.

X-Ray structure determination : Accurate lattice parameters were determined from least squares refinements of well-centered reflections in the ranges $2.91 \leq \theta \leq 27.49$ for both AT-DNB and AT-DNS. 5681 (AT-DNB) and 5944 (AT-DNS) unique reflections were measured of which 2289 (AT-DNB) and 1977 (AT-DNS) had $I > 3.00 \sigma(I)$. These observed reflections were used for structure determination and refinements. Atomic positional parameters, bond lengths and angles, anisotropic temperature factors and calculated and observed structure factors are given in Supplementary Tables (CCDC no. : 196940 for 1 and CCDC no. : 196941 for 2). All diagrams and calculations were performed using maXus crys-

tallographic software package (Nonius, Delft & MacScience, Japan). The structures were determined by direct methods SIR 92⁸ and refined by full matrix least-squares methods maXus⁹. The displacement factors of non-hydrogen atoms of the two complexes were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The hydrogen atoms were refined isotropically.

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